

THE TYPES OF LOANS WORDS, THEIR NATURALIZATION IN ENGLISH AND ITS ROLE IN COMMUNICATION

Maxmudova Zilola Shuxrat qizi

Toshkent viloyati Chirchiq davlat pedagogika instituti magistranti

Pochta: mahmudovazilola62@gmail.com

Annotation

In many cases a borrowed word especially one borrowed long ago is practically indistinguishable from a native word without a thorough etymological analysis (street, school, face). The number of borrowings in the vocabulary of a language and the role played by them is determined by the historical development of the nation speaking the language. The most effective way of borrowing is direct borrowing from another language as the result of contacts with the people of another country or with their literature.

Key words: communication, loans words, literature,

Introduction

Etymologically the vocabulary of the English language is far from being homogeneous. It consists of two layers - the native stock of words and the borrowed stock of words. Numerically the borrowed stock of words is considerably larger than the native stock of words. In fact native words comprise only 30 % of the total number of words in the English vocabulary but the native words form the bulk of the most frequent words actually used in speech and writing. Besides the native words have a wider range of lexical and grammatical valency, they are highly polysemantic and productive in forming word clusters and set expressions.

Borrowed words (or loan words or borrowings) are words taken over from another language and modified according to the patterns of the receiving language.

In many cases a borrowed word especially one borrowed long ago is practically indistinguishable from a native word without a thorough etymological analysis (street, school, face). The number of borrowings in the vocabulary of a language and the role played by them is determined by the historical development of the nation

speaking the language. The most effective way of borrowing is direct borrowing from another language as the result of contacts with the people of another country or with their literature. But a word may also be borrowed indirectly not from the source language

but through another language.

Methods

When analysing borrowed words one must distinguish between the two terms - "source of borrowing" and "origin of borrowing". The first term is applied to the language from which the word was immediately borrowed, the second - to the language to which the word may be ultimately traced e.g. table - source of borrowing - French, origin of borrowing - Latin elephant - source of borrowing - French, origin - Egypt convene - source of borrowing - French, origin - Latin. The closer the two interacting languages are in structure the easier it is for words of one language to penetrate into the other. There are different ways of classifying the borrowed stock of words. First of all the borrowed stock of words may be classified according to the nature of the borrowing itself as borrowings proper, translation loans and semantic loans. Translation loans are words or expressions formed from the elements existing in the English language according to the patterns of the source language (the moment of truth. A semantic loan is the borrowing of a meaning for a word already existing in the English language e.g. the compound word shock brigade which existed in the English language with the meaning "source of borrowing" acquired a new meaning "origin of borrowing" which it borrowed from the Russian language. Latin Loans are classified into the subgroups. 1. Early Latin Loans. Those are the words which came into English through the language of Anglo-Saxon tribes. The tribes had been in contact with Roman civilisation and had adopted several Latin words denoting objects belonging to that civilisation long before the invasion of Angles, Saxons and Jutes into Britain (cup, kitchen, mill, port, wine). 2. Later Latin Borrowings. To this group belong the words which penetrated the English vocabulary in the sixth and seventh centuries, when the people of England were converted to Christianity (priest,

bishop, nun, candle). 3.The third period of Latin includes words which came into English due to two historical events: the Norman conquest in 1066 and the Renaissance or the Revival of Learning. Some words came into English through French but some were taken directly from Latin (major, minor, intelligent, permanent). 4.The Latest Stratum of Latin Words. The words of this period are mainly abstract and scientific words (nylon, molecular, vaccine, phenomenon, vacuum). Norman-French Borrowings may be subdivided into subgroups: 1.Early loans - 12th - 15th century 2.Later loans - beginning from the 16th century. The Early French borrowings are simple short words, naturalised in accordance with the English language system (state, power, war, pen, river) Later French borrowings can be identified by their peculiarities of form and pronunciation (regime, police, ballet, scene, bourgeois).

There are different ways of classifying the borrowed stock of words. First of all the borrowed stock of words may be classified according to the nature of the borrowing itself as borrowings proper, translation loans and semantic loans. Translation loans are words or expressions formed from the elements existing in the English language according to the patterns of the source language (the moment of truth . A semantic loan is the borrowing of a meaning for a word already existing in the English language e.g. the compound word shock brigade which existed in the English language with the meaning acquired a new meaning which it borrowed from the Russian language. Early Latin Loans. Those are the words which came into English through the language of Anglo-Saxon tribes. The tribes had been in contact with Roman civilisation and had adopted several Latin words denoting objects belonging to that civilisation long before the invasion of Angles, Saxons and Jutes into Britain (*cup, kitchen, mill, port, wine*).

1.Later Latin Borrowings. To this group belong the words which penetrated the English vocabulary in the sixth and seventh centuries, when the people of England were converted to Christianity (*priest, bishop, nun, candle*). historical events: the Norman conquest in 1066 and the Renaissance or the Revival of

Learning. Some words came into English through French but some were taken directly from Latin (*major, minor, intelligent, permanent*).

2. The Latest Stratum of Latin Words. The words of this period are mainly abstract and scientific words (*nylon, molecular, vaccine, phenomenon, vacuum*). Norman-French Borrowings may be subdivided into subgroups: Lexical correlations are defined as lexical units from different languages which are phonetically and semantically related. Semantically Russian- English lexical correlations are various. They may denote everyday objects and commonly used things; *brutal* -грубый, *cold* - холодный, *ground* - грунт, *kettle* -котел, *kitchen* - кухня, *money* - монета, *sister* - сестра, *wolf*- волк etc. For instance the word was at first indivisible in English, which is seen from the forms, entered by some dictionaries. Later on the word came to be divided into the morphological elements. The new morphological division can be accounted for by the existence of a number of words containing these elements (*bolshevism, bolshevist, sputnik*, Assimilation is the process of changing the adopted word. The process of assimilation of borrowings includes changes in sound form of morphological structure, grammar characteristics, meaning and usage.

Phonetic assimilation comprises changes in sound form and stress. Sounds that were alien to the English language were fitted into its scheme of sounds, e.g. In the recent French borrowings *communique, cafe* the long [e] and [e] are rendered with the help of [ei]. The accent is usually transferred to the first syllable in the words from foreign sources. The process of semantic assimilation has many forms: narrowing of meanings (usually polysemantic words are borrowed in one of the meanings); specialisation or generalisation of meanings, acquiring new meanings in the recipient language, shifting a primary meaning to the position of a secondary meaning.

Completely assimilated borrowings are the words, which have undergone all types of assimilation. Such words are frequently used and are stylistically neutral, they may occur as dominant words in a synonymic group. They take an active part in word-formation. Partially assimilated borrowings are the words which lack one of the types of assimilation.

They are subdivided into the groups:

1) Borrowings not assimilated semantically (e.g. *shah, rajah*). Such words usually denote objects and notions peculiar to the country from which they came.

2) Loan words not assimilated grammatically, e.g. nouns borrowed from Latin or Greek which keep their original plural forms (*datum - data, phenomenon - phenomena*).

3) Loan words not completely assimilated phonetically. These words contain peculiarities in stress, combinations of sounds that are not standard for English (*machine, camouflage, tobacco*).

4) Loan words not completely assimilated graphically (e.g. *ballet, cafe, cliché*). Barbarisms are words from other languages used by the English people in conversation or in writing but not assimilated in any way, and for which there are corresponding English equivalents e.g. *ciao* Italian - *good-bye* English,

Reference

1. Allopenna, P. D., Magnuson, J. S., and Tanenhaus, M. K. 1998. Tracking the time course of spoken word recognition using eye movements: evidence for continuous mapping models. *Journal of Memory and Language*, 38: 419–439.

2. Barron, F., and Harrington, D. M. 1981. Creativity, intelligence, and personality. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 32: 439–476.

3. Berger, R. M., and Guilford, J. P. 1969. *Pilot titles*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sheridan Psychological Services.

4. Bialystok, E. 1988. Levels of bilingualism and levels of linguistic awareness. *Developmental Psychology*, 24: 560–567.

Bialystok, E., Craik, F. I. M., Grady, C., Chau, W., Ishii, R., Gunji, A., and Pantev, C. 2005. Effect of bilingualism on cognitive control in the Simon task: evidence from MEG. *NeuroImage*, 24: 40–49.

5. Bialystok, E., Craik, F. I. M., Klein, R., and Viswanathan, M. 2004. Bilingualism, aging, and cognitive control: evidence from the simon task. *Psychology and Aging*, 19: 290–303.
6. R., Biardeau, A., and Grainger, J. 1997. Masked orthographic priming in bilingual word recognition. *Memory and Cognition*, 25, 447–457.
7. Birman, D., and Trickett, E. J. 2001. Cultural transitions in first-generation immigrants: acculturation of Soviet Jewish refugee adolescents and parents. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 32: 456–477.